

Enter into the Indian Textile Business through Location Economy Strategy: An Opportunity for Foreign Investors

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Abstract

The document seeks to capture a basic set of elements defending the location economy strategy as production opportunity in the Indian textile industry for foreign investors. Indian Textile Industry contributes 14% to industrial production, 17% to export earnings and direct employ over 35 million people. India ranks first in worldwide production (2008) of jute (1.7 bill kg) and second of cotton (5.0 bill kg) and third of silk (17 bill kg). *Location economy* involves the cost advantage of producing a good value activity at the optimal position. Two elements were taken into consideration to describe the optimal location economy analysis in the industry, they are: Indian textile value chain and three industry factors: *production, government initiatives and foreign direct investment policy*. Vast sourcing of raw material, loom and spinning capacity and mass production of apparel are the attractive niches along the value chain. Low total labor cost compare with other countries, intense government initiatives and attractive foreign direct investment policy represent the main strengths of industry factors persuading foreign investors. Nevertheless, questions are remain about the elements composing the “easy of doing business” in the country when the environmental analysis was performed. Indian textile industry provides a significant opportunity for foreign investors who can overcome the challenges to play business through location economy strategy.

Key words: India, textile, production, location economy, foreigner investment.

I. India – Economy Overview.

The Republic of India recent macroeconomic growth and positive trade performance has attracted the attention of global analysts. First of all, the main record is attached at to upward value trend of the overall economic output (GDP). It reveals an average growth of 8.7% (PPP) over the past twenty years occupying the fourth place in the classified rank of countries by GDP 2008². Secondly, the merchandise exports increased from US\$ 63.8bn (2003-04) to US\$162.9bn

(2007-08) at an average annual growth rate of 26.4%.³ Nevertheless, challenges are also present in the economy scenery (2008): unemployment 6.8%, public debt 78% of GDP (federal and state debt) and inflation rate (consumer prices): 7.8%⁴. Addressing demographic issues, India is the second most populous country (1.2 billion⁵) where most of

Table 1	
Basic Economic Indicators	
Currency	1 Indian Rupee (INR) (RS) = 100 Paise
GDP	\$3.209 trillion (2008 est.)
GDP growth	6.7% (2009)
Labor force	523.5 million (2008 est.)
Labor force by occupation	agriculture: 60%, industry: 12%, services: 28% (2003)
Foreign Trade Indicators	
Exports	\$175.7 billion f.o.b. ¹ (2008 est.)
Main export partners	US 15%, the People's Republic of China 8.7%, UAE 8.7%, UK 4.4% (2007)
Imports	\$287.5 billion (2008 est.)
Main import partners	People's Republic of China 10.6%, US 7.8%, Germany 4.4%, (2007)
Source: CIA World Fact Book – 2008 <i>Values are in US dollars</i>	

the residents are financially sustained by the traditional *run – family business* in farming village (Table 1) causing evident per capital income regional variations. On one side, what has increased to Rs. 33, 283 in 2007–08 and went up 60% since 2003-04⁶. India has a 300 million middle-class growing at an annual rate of 5%.⁷ On the other side, 456 million Indians (42% total population)

¹ Free On Board
² IMF (2009)
³ Department of Commerce (2009)
⁴ CIA World Fact Book – 2008
⁵ United Nations (2009)
⁶ Financial Express (2009)
⁷ Wilkinson J and D. Keilor (2008)

live under the global poverty line (\$1.25 p/day).⁸ Undoubtedly, Indian economic performance has had a notable global role which in addition has lead intense debates about the sustainability of its future.

II. Giant Indian Textile Industry

Pre – liberalized economic period (1980s – 1990s) was influenced by protective socialist policies. Rajiv Gandhi government (1984 – 1989) initiated the revival of the foreign policy through an economic liberalization⁹. Nevertheless, a fiscal imbalance over the 1980s provoked a severe crisis where exchange rate adjustments were made¹⁰¹¹. Prime Minister, P. V. Narasimha Rao, and Finance Minister, Dr Manmohan Singh’s (1990) immediate response was to secure an emergency loan of \$2.2 billion from the IMF¹² followed by various reforms such as international trade and privatization. After twenty years of redirecting the Indian economic structure, the impact has been reflected over *key* industries. Manufacturing sector became a pillar for the commercial and production activity of the country (FIG 1). The average growth (2008) is estimated 7%¹³ contributing 25% to GDP. Astonishingly, 65% of the total exports classified as goods are manufactured products. It achieved a notable double-digit gain during 2005-2006¹⁴ estimating \$180 billion investment opportunity over the next five years.¹⁵

FIG 1

⁸ World Bank (2005)

⁹ Cultural India (2010)

¹⁰ Cerra V and Chaman S (2002)

¹¹ Major depreciation of the rupee history

¹² The Hindu Business Line (2009)

¹³ Textile Association India (2007)

¹⁴ Waldam C (2009)

¹⁵ Indian Brand Equity Foundation (2009)

Source: Reserve Bank of India, Global Insight and MAPI calculations

Indian Textile Industry (included in manufacturing categories) contributes 14% to industrial production, 4% to GDP, and 17% to export earnings. It provides direct employment to over 35 million people. The total value of the industry is US\$ 52 billion¹⁶ and targets US\$ 6 billion of foreign direct investment (FDI)¹⁷.

Table 2			
Fiber Strength of India			
	Production during 2008	% Share in the world	World rank
Jute (Kenaf and allied fibers)	1.7 Billion Kg.	56%	1
Cotton	5.0 Billion Kg.	22%	2 (China – 30%)
Silk	17 Million Kg.	13%	2 (China – 82%)
Cellulosic Fibres/Yarns	.33 Billion Kg.	12%	2 (China – 45%)
Synthetic Fibers/Yarns	2.4 Billion Kg.	6%	4 (China – 48%)

SOURCE: Textile Commissioner (2009)

Information in Table 2 supports the Indian strong position as multi – fiber world producer even though the industry is dominated by small scale players across the value chain. The two main drivers leading the India textile industry are: i) competitive spinning industry: global share of industry contribution is 20% to the world spindleage (166.36 million spindles)¹⁸ and ii) low labor

¹⁶ Ministry of Textile (2010)

¹⁷ Ibid

¹⁸ Jayavarthanavelu D (2003)

cost US\$0.59 per hour¹⁹. During 2007-08 exports were US\$22.13 billion expecting to grow at a rate of 11% by 2010²⁰ and increase from US\$ 90billion to US\$100 billion in the next 25 years. According to WTO, the Indian global trade share was 4% and clothing 2.8% ranking 7th and 6th respectively. The main markets (2008) for Indian textile products are European Union with 34% (where they rank 3rd) and United States 25% (where they rank 2nd). The imports in 2008 accounted to US\$3.33 billion, 49% yarn and fabrics and 45% raw material and semi raw-material showing a steady decadency.²¹ Indian leadership as a fiber producer and textile exporter places it as a global competitor.

¹⁹ Value Partners (2006)

²⁰ Dun & Bradstreet (2010)

²¹ Ibid

III. Location Economy Strategy

Nowadays, it is common practice to split up and locate the industry value chain around the world producing a significant standardization of commercial process and activities among countries. One way to enter into the international arena is done by manufacturing a product in a country which possesses the comparative advantage. The formal definition of the term “location economy” involves the cost advantage from producing a value creation activity at the optimal location. The main features are:

- Minimization of unit costs.
- Offering a standardized product to the global market place.

Two elements were taken into consideration to describe the optimal location economy analysis in the industry. The first is the Indian textile value chain. It has been growing across a variety of segments in the textile value chain (FIG 2):

Source: Indian Brand Equity – Textile and Apparels 2008

The constant growth of the offer (small scale industry) and supportive environment (abundance in raw material and government policies) produce attractive segments in the Indian textile industry for investment.

The second element, points to three factors in the Indian textile industry under study, they are:

i. Production

Particularly, Indian textile industry possesses two main strengths: production capacity and low cost.

In terms of transformation capacity of tangibles, the main strategic sectors are:²²

- Spinning: 40 million spindles. Independent spinning mills account for about 75% of total capacity and 92% of the total production.
- Looms: 3.9 million handlooms.
- Apparel Making: 25,000 domestic manufacturers, 48,000 fabricators and around 4,000 manufacturers/exporters. 80% of the total units are small operations.

In terms of costs:

- Low total labor cost compared with other countries is distinctive due to intensive activity (offer), low wage industry and predominantly unskilled manpower (FIG 3).
- Large participation of females and migrants in the industry. It is the second to provide employment after agriculture.

FIG 3

²² Indian Brand Equity Foundation (2008)

Source: Indian Brand Equity – Textile and Apparels 2008

ii. *Government initiatives*

To promote the Industry the Government of India has taken various supportive initiatives:

National Textile Policy (NTP) 2000. The aim was to facilitate the sustainability for manufacture and export of clothing²³. It would endeavor to achieve the target of textile and apparel exports from the present level of \$50 billion by 2010²⁴. The great achievements concerning are:

- Reduction in customs duty from 20% to 15% for fibers, yarns, and garments and 20% on textile machinery.
- Reduction in corporate tax rate from 35% to 30% with 10% surcharge.

Technology Upgradation Fund Scheme (TUFS)

It was founded with the purpose to help in the transition from a quantitatively restricted textiles trade to market driven global merchandise. It is estimated that this will ensure a growth rate of 16% in the sector.²⁵ It increased to Rs. 1,090 crores in 2008-09 from Rs. 911 crores in 2007-08. Rs 916 crore has been disbursed for technology up gradation²⁶.

Scheme for Integrated Textile Parks (SITP)

It is being implemented to facilitate setting up of textile units with appropriate support infrastructure. Industry Associations / Group of Entrepreneurs are the main promoters²⁷ A total of 30 parks attract investment of Rs.15435 crores and an annual production of Rs.23600 crore²⁸.

NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF FASHION TECHNOLOGY (NIFT)

²³ Indian Embassy in USA (2010)

²⁴ India in Business (2009)

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Ibid

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Ibid

It was set up in 1986 in collaboration with the Fashion Technology (FT), New York, to train professionals to meet the requirements of the worldwide textile industry. The Institute has pioneered the evolution of fashion business in the country through its seven centers network²⁹

iii. Foreign Direct Investment Policy

In recognition of the important role of Foreign Direct Investment in accelerating economic growth of the country, Government of India approves 100% FDI freely in spinning, weaving, processing, garments and knitting sector under the automatic route for both new ventures and existing companies.

Foreign Investment proposals are received by the Board. Within 15 days of receipt, the Administrative Ministries must offer their comments either prior to and/or in the meeting of the FIPB (Foreign Investment Promotion Board) which the approval is required³⁰. FIPB. The final decisions of the Government on FDI proposals are communicated to the applicant within six weeks.³¹

As a result of the various policies initiatives taken raise the **100% export oriented units/ export processing zones/ special economic zones**. The minimum outlay required is Rs.100 crores and 5 lakh sq.mts, built up area. The central principles are³²:

“100% Export Oriented Units (EOUs) and units in the Export Processing Zones (EPZs)/Special Economic Zones (SEZs), enjoy a package of incentives and facilities, which include duty free imports of all types of capital goods, raw material, and consumables in addition to tax holidays against export”.

²⁹ Ibid

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Minister of Commerce and Industry (2010)

³² Ibid

“100% FDI is permitted under automatic route for setting up of industrial park/industrial model town/special economic zone in the country. To encourage investment in this sector, 100% income tax exemption for 10 years within a block of 15 years is also granted for the industrial parks set up during the period 1.4.1977 to 31.3.2006”.

IV. Important considerations

Sustaining the impressive rate of growth over the past years, Indian textile industry is actually experiencing a huge potential capacity of production. Nevertheless, questions remain about the elements composing the “ease of doing business” in the country. Relevant elements are:

- Because India is a vast territory, there are significant constraints on logistics operations. More incentives need to be given as logistic costs are very high and present incentives are not sufficient to cover high logistic cost.
- Even though, Government of India has adopted simplification of procedures and formalities for the exporters, still there are regulatory and bureaucratic barriers. They are part of the implication in the evolution process of an emerging economy and must be taken into consideration.
- The industry is dominated by many small and medium sized firms which expose an evident lack of upgradation. A backward machinery textile mill will not be able to support an accelerated growth global path.
- An indirect factor having impact on the business transaction is regarding the efficiency of service companies such as: financial services and cargo and shipping agents. Effective

improvements must be made to eradicate low productivity, overstaffing and excess capacity.

Indian textile industry provides a significant opportunity for foreign investors who can overcome the challenges to enter into the Indian textile business through location economy strategy.

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